

Expansion of olive orchards and their impact on the cultivation and landscape through a case study in the countryside of Cordoba (Spain)

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ABSTRACT

The sustainability of farming systems has been enhanced by legislation on different scales, but at the same time these policies also promote more productive systems through farming intensification (e.g., use of irrigation or high tree densities). This is the case of olive orchard expansion on cereal cropland in recent decades. This study analyses the impact of this expansion on orchard characteristics and landscape elements in a case study in the 'campiña' of Cordoba in Southern Spain based on the evolution of their surface and typologies during the period from 2005 to 2018. Our results show that olive orchards doubled their surface after the 13-year period, from 7997.8 to 16,447.6 ha. On average the new orchards tended to have higher plant density and a more frequent use of irrigation in the study period. Despite this trend towards intensification, the current situation shows a majority of rainfed (76.4%) and medium tree densities, 120–200 trees/ha, (42.7%) of the area. Nevertheless, newly intensified orchards are arising in the region, resulting in a mosaic of orchards of different characteristics (slope, tree density, soil type) and agricultural managements (irrigation, ground cover vegetation).

In addition, this characterization was complemented with an inventory of the existing semi-natural elements associated with these orchards to identify the current state of the regional agricultural landscape. A total number of 507 isolated trees and different linear and polygonal landscape elements (343.9 km and 714.0 ha, respectively), mainly segmented, were inventoried. From these polygonal landscape elements, a significant fraction (e.g., slopes, gullies, water banks and non-productive strips/faces) remains unvegetated (57%). Therefore, these elements must be considered in multiscale agricultural policies as potential restoration areas to enhance ecosystem service provisioning.

1. Introduction

Improvement in the agricultural landscape has become a matter of increasing interest at European level in recent decades, through different strategies developed within a general framework of improving ecosystem services in agricultural areas. Among these strategies a key one is the European Landscape Convention (Council of Europe, 2000), which was designed as an integral tool for protection, management and planning, encompassing the entire landscape. In the same direction, the European Commission and the Member States have contributed to the progressive integration of the importance of the environment and the conservation of biodiversity of agricultural landscapes in the Common Agricultural Policy, CAP (European Commission, 2019).

Since the CAP reform of 2013, the orientation towards achieving environmental goals has been intensified in favor of sustainable resource

management, improvement of biodiversity and climate change mitigation. This orientation reinforces the relevance of landscape diversification through vegetation, which in addition to its esthetic component, is a major factor for improving the provision of different ecosystem services in agricultural areas (MEA, 2005). Together, these policies pursue the design and implementation of strategies that increase synergies and maximize coherence between the objectives of biodiversity conservation, agricultural production, and the development of rural areas. Despite this increasing interest, several studies have shown variability in the impact of the CAP on promoting diversity of agricultural landscapes. In fact, in a recent study by Gómez et al. (2021) it was highlighted that there was a need to provide a more detailed description of agricultural practices and their link to the different olive orchards' typologies in the countryside of Cordoba and other typical growing area of Andalusia (Estepa) to improve the provision of ecosystem services and to

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implement sustainable practices effectively. In the study of Gómez-Limón et al. (2012) the authors concluded that effective structural policy measures to improve eco-efficient farms should be focused on the promotion of specific practices at farm level and not only based on classical targeting criteria (e.g., Cohen et al., 2008 who found a high diversity of flora growing below the olive trees, thanks to the diversity of individual practices in the management of olive growing, partly encouraged by conditionality requirements of the CAP).

However, despite the efforts made by olive growers and environmentally-friendly policies regarding the environmental impact of olive-growing activity and the improvement of natural capital, there is still need for improving specific agricultural practices (e.g., soil management, irrigation, fertilization, etc.). The optimization of these practices must be in favor of ecosystem service provisioning as crop yield, soil and water quality, biodiversity or preservation of cultural landscapes (Carmona-Torres et al., 2014; Montanaro et al., 2017).

The post 2020 CAP (European Commission, 2019) highlights the importance of reaching European-wide environmental goals. Its main objectives include achieving a better targeting of subsidies to active farmers and a more prominent role of environmental aspects through a specific payment, 'greening', to achieve a more sustainable CAP. This orientation towards a more sustainable and competitive agricultural sector is a key contribution to the European Green Deal. This will result in stronger environmental commitments by Member States introducing instruments like mandatory eco-schemes and enhanced conditionality.

To reach the maximum benefit of these environmental measures, the multifunctionality of agriculture and rural landscapes must be monitored to review the different applied research approaches, addressing rural sustainable development (Song et al., 2020). Nevertheless, these authors highlight the lack of commonality in the research approaches assessing multifunctionality of agriculture to support not only decision makers, such as policy makers, but also farmers as individuals (farm level) or as collectives (landscape scale). In this regard, as mentioned for local management practices at farm scale, landscape management strategies must also be adapted according to the particular rural landscape features (e.g., character, functionality, etc.; Di Fazio and Modica, 2018). This is of vital importance especially in landscapes where economic activity, local traditions and popular knowledge are strongly linked and identified as the main income of the region, as olive orchards and olive oil are.

In Andalusia (southern Spain), olive growing is a vital sector in the socioeconomic, environmental, and cultural fabric of the entire region since it represents approximately 26% of agricultural production and employs almost 32% of agricultural labor (Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca y Desarrollo Rural, 2015). In addition to the production of high-quality food, the cultivation of olive trees provides numerous positive externalities such as the economic viability of rural areas, the maintenance of the rural population and the provision of cultural and esthetic services (López-Pintor et al., 2018).

Traditionally olive orchards have been managed in order to optimize olive yield through optimization of the water balance through low tree densities, control of canopy size and bare soils. This management combining some topographic and climatic factors (moderate to high slopes and high intensity rains) has led to soil degradation through soil erosion and reduction of the provision of ecosystem services (Gómez and Giráldez, 2009; Gómez-Limón et al., 2012; Gómez, 2016). However, the Andalusian agricultural landscape is still undergoing significant changes due to the dynamic nature of its agricultural sector. Among the drivers for this change are the intensification of olive cultivation (e.g., mechanization, irrigation, increase in planting density, changes in soil management techniques, etc.) driven by a combination of market forces and CAP and other national and regional policies (Lefebvre et al., 2012; Assandri et al., 2017), which is resulting in changes in the cultivated areas of different crops and their management. For instance, in recent years olive orchards have been expanding their cultivated area upstream of the Guadalquivir river valley (Guzmán and Zoido-Naranjo, 2013)

modifying the agricultural landscape. In this area cereals and olives used to coexist, with cereals in the soils of greater agronomic aptitude in the less sloping areas and olives in the more sloping ones. However, as a consequence of low cereal prices (ASAJA, 2017; EUROSTAT, 2020) and a relatively greater profitability of olive cultivation, this picture has changed in the last decade. This recent development has been aligned with the evolution towards intensification of the olive sector and modification of Andalusia's landscapes since the 1960s, in which production has increased faster than the olive-tree surface (Infante-Amate et al., 2016). Fleskens (2007) noted that in areas where intensive olive monoculture has replaced the traditional mosaic landscape, biodiversity and landscape values have been substantially reduced. This double change in surface expansion and intensified olive farming practices casts doubts on the sustainability of such important changes, for instance analysing its long-term impact on yields (Mairech et al., 2020). It also raises the need to update knowledge on this expansion of olive-growing areas and accompanying soil management that might have changed significantly in recent years.

This study aims to provide an updated overview of the evolution of olive orchard typologies from 2005 to 2018 and the potential of landscape elements associated with olive farms improving ecosystem service provisioning in a representative Western Mediterranean area. To do this, the particular objectives are the following ones: (i) to develop an inventory of the existing olive orchards in 2018 characterizing some of their key agronomic and edapho-geomorphological variables; (ii) to analyse and compare these variables in relation to the orchards existing in 2005; (iii) to evaluate the use of temporary cover crops through vegetation indices to explore their relationship with olive orchard typology; and (iv) to make an inventory of the existing landscape elements in 2018 associated with the olive orchards and relate them to some agronomic and edapho-geomorphological variables.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Description of the study area

The countryside or, hereafter, 'campiña' of Cordoba (Southern Spain) occupies an approximate surface area of 82,000 ha and is delimited by the administrative boundary of the municipality of Cordoba, except for the North and Northwest which are delimited by the left bank of the Guadalquivir river, Fig. 1.

The climate of the area is a Mediterranean climate (Csa) according to the Köppen classification (Gómez-Zotano et al., 2015) with cold winters and hot summers, with significant daily temperature fluctuations ranging from 0 °C to 40 °C, respectively. Average annual precipitation and potential evapotranspiration ranges from 600 to 800 mm and 800–900 mm respectively (Consejería de Agricultura, Ganadería, Pesca y Desarrollo Sostenible, 2007a,b). The dominant soil types are Vertic soils, followed in extension by Calcic Regosols and Calcic Cambisols, with a moderate presence of Fluvisols and Luvisols (Consejería de Medio Ambiente, 2005; IUSS, 2015). Its rolling landscape is characterized by a clear edaphic and geomorphological continuity without abrupt changes. This area provides optimal conditions for the cultivation of cereal-based rotations, mostly rainfed, (Guzmán, 2004) although in recent decades it has been undergoing a transformation with an increase in the surface area of tree crops, being mainly olive trees.

2.2. Characterization of olive orchards in the study area

The characterization of the area consisted of the digitization, inventory, and description of olive farms on the cartographic bases described in Table 1. To do this, a geographic information system was created using the free software QGIS v.2.18.15 'Las Palmas', its complements and decision support tools (Table S1). A virtual grid of 4.6 × 7.3 km was established to carry out a systematic analysis of each olive orchard in each grid for the whole study area, campiña, Fig. 1. In

Fig. 1. City of Cordoba (blue) and zoom to the study area (delimited by the black line).

this analysis, the elementary unit was the basic cadastral unit (agricultural enclosure) as defined for the implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy regulations (Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca y Desarrollo Rural, 2018). The inventory was based on a previous inventory carried out in the summer of 2005 by Mora Jordano (2009) and from the information available on the use of land, farm boundaries, roads, waterways, and other landscape elements, all of them collected in the regional Geographic Information System developed for the Common Agricultural Policy in 2018 (hereafter SIGPAC 2018). The olive orchard surface area was determined in each grid, incorporating olive farms not

yet declared in SIGPAC but visible in Google Earth Pro (December 2017–December 2018) at the beginning of the study, that of July 21st, 2018. To all the farms included in the inventory, the following complementary information was added or updated to the GIS layer's attribute table to characterize and describe the different existing orchard typologies in the area for existing farms in 2005 and new ones in 2018: tree density, surface, average slope, dominant soil type(s) and irrigation. It is worth noting that irrigation in olive trees in the area is always deficit irrigation within the range of 1000–3000 m³/ha yr.

Table 1
Cartographic resources used.

Format	List of files	Source
Vectorial	Last update of the National Topographic Map; scale 1:25000: Sheets 0922–4, 0923–1, 0923–2, 0923–3, 0923–4, 0924–3, 0924–4, 0943–2, 0943–4, 0944–1, 0944–2, 0944–3, 0944–4, 0945–1, 0966–2.	National Center for Geographic Information (CNIG): https://www.centrodedescargas.cnig.es/CentroDescargas/
	Geographic Information System of the municipality of Cordoba (SIGPAC, 2018): • Year 2005 • Year 2018	Consejería de Agricultura, Ganadería, Pesca y Desarrollo Sostenible (Junta de Andalucía), 2005 (personal communication) and for 2018 in: https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/areas/politica-agraria-comun/paginas/sigpac-descarga-informacion-geografica-shapes-provincias.html https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=181bc6bdc1b64072a086881ba0b1cd39
	Great rivers of Spain-ETRS89 UTM 30 N.	Spanish National Geographic Institute (IGN): https://www.ign.es
Raster	Jurisdictional Boundaries of Spain. Ortophoto <i>National Plan of Aerial Orthophotography</i> (PNOA) ETRS89, Time zone 30, Time zone 50: Sheets 0922, 0923, 0924, 0943, 0944, 0945. PNOA Digital Elevation Model 5 m: Sheets 0922, 0923, 0924, 0943, 0944, 0945.	National Center for Geographic Information (CNIG): https://www.centrodedescargas.cnig.es/CentroDescargas/
WMS	Map of Soils of Andalusia. Cartography of the Vegetation associated to Wetlands of Andalusia	Environmental Information Network of Andalusia (REDIAM): http://descargas.ediam.cica.es/repo/s/RUR

2.3. Soil management determination

In addition to the characteristics mentioned above, a discrimination of soil management at each plot between bare soil or temporary cover crop in the alleys during fall and winter, the two common types of soil management in the area (Gómez, 2016), was made. This was carried out evaluating the presence or absence of vegetation in the orchard lines during mid-winter using Sentinel-2-L-2A freely available images with resolution ranging according to the band between 10 and 60 m (although almost all the ones used in this study had a 10 m resolution), and comparing vegetation indexes during winter, the rainy period when the cover crops should be present, and in summer when the only green vegetation present is that of the olive trees.

Vegetation indices are quantitative measures based on numerical values of images allowing the measurement of plants' ground cover, vigor, or their biomass (Silleos et al., 2006). They are derived from spectral bands, which are combined numerically to generate a single value that quantitatively shows a representative value of the vegetation per pixel. These indices are correlated with different characteristics of the vegetation of agronomic, ecological, or environmental interest (Baret and Guyot, 1991), the most commonly used being the following: normalized difference vegetation index *NDVI*, enhanced vegetation index *EVI*, grassland curing index *GCI*, green normalized difference *GNDVI*, normalized difference water index *NDWI*, soil-adjusted vegetation index *SAVI*, atmospherically resistant vegetation index *ARVI* and structural independent pigment index *SIPI*. All these indexes used data from bandwidths at 10 m spatial resolution, with the exception of *NDWI* which used data from bandwidths at an original spatial resolution of 10 and 20 m.

In our study, we followed a similar methodology to that used by Carvacho Bart and Sánchez Martínez (2010), who compared five vegetation indices (*NDVI*, *SAVI*, *ARVI*, *GNDVI* and *EVI*) to evaluate the evolution of the ground covers of the years 2001, 2003 and 2005 in agricultural, livestock and forestry areas of Chile before determining the index best suited for our purposes. To do this, we carried out a preliminary evaluation of eight vegetation indexes (*NDVI*, *EVI*, *GCI*, *GNDVI*, *NDWI*, *SAVI*, *ARVI* and *SIPI*) hereafter called calibration, to explore the best index to identify the presence of a cover crop in the orchard lanes during winter. This selection was based on the study of Carvacho Bart and Sánchez Martínez (2010) and other vegetation indices reported in the literature (e.g., *GCI* in Schmidt et al., 2010; *NDWI* in Vemula, 2018 or *SIPI* in Marino et al., 2014) used in agricultural studies for different ground cover assessments.

This analysis was aimed at identifying the potential of the indices to integrate the differences between late winter (in which the signal of living vegetation reflects the signal of the tree and vegetation ground cover) and summer (in which the only green vegetation on the farm is

due to olive trees, regardless of the use of temporary cover crops which were removed in early spring). Afterwards, we carried out a validation exercise with images of a different season, hereafter called validation, with the best performing index to determine the thresholds to determine among soil management classes and the accuracy in the classification of soil management in different orchards.

2.3.1. Calibration

Thirty-four sampling areas in olive orchards with a known soil management verified after field inspection over consecutive years from 2015 to 2020 were selected within the study area. Ten were with bare soil in the lanes, twelve with partial temporary cover crops (understood as alternate lanes of bare soil and cover crop management or narrow, less than 1 m wide, cover crop strips in all the lanes) and another twelve used temporary cover crop in all the lanes. The location of the sampling area on these farms is shown in Table S2. The values of the above indices were determined on these farms using Sentinel-2-L-2A images corresponding to 21-II-2019 (winter) and 18-VII-2018 (summer). The Sentinel-2 L2A images (with a spatial resolution of 20 m per pixel) with the required spectral bands were obtained from the web platform of the Earth Observation System (EOS, 2019) using the EOS Browser, each one accompanied by its respective metadata file. For each farm, the vegetation index was calculated for a square area of 100 × 100 m at each sampling location point. This was performed using the raster calculator and the 'Zone Statistics' plugin of the QGIS v. 2.18.15 'Las Palmas'.

We evaluated different combinations (vegetation index value in winter divided by value in summer, or value in winter minus value in summer) for each index in late winter (February 21st, 2019) and summer (July 18th, 2018). The three best performing indexes (*NDVI*, *GCI*, *EVI*) were analysed to determine the one with the best predictive capability to distinguish soil management under two different classification strategies:

- between bare soil and cover crop in the lane in winter,
- bare soil, cover crop in all the lanes, or partial cover crops (understood as alternate lanes of bare soil and cover crop management or narrow, less than 1 m wide, cover crop strips in all the lanes).

To analyse existing significant differences among the three pre-selected indices comparing different soil management in winter, a Kruskal Wallis test for independent samples was performed ($P < 0.05$) using MS Excel © and 'MegaStat' plugin. Additionally, the threshold values among classes were determined to optimize the percentage of well classified farms.

2.3.2. Validation

Once the index with the best predictive capabilities (*EVI*) was

determined, it was validated by recalculating the same index for the same thirty-four points used in the calibration exercise. This analysis was made using images from a different season from those used in the calibration stage, February 21st, 2018 (late winter) and July 21st, 2017 (summer) to verify the robustness of the approach. In all cases, the vegetation index was calculated (for each farm) from the raster layers of the spectral band values and the vegetation index was calculated as the average of a square area of 100×100 m at each measurement point. This was performed using the raster calculator and the 'Zone Statistics' plugin of the QGIS v. 2.18.15 'Las Palmas'. From this data, the predictive capability for determining the soil management during winter using the two different classification strategies (see below) was established, using the threshold values between classes determined in the calibration stage:

- a) between bare soil and cover crop in the lane in winter,
- b) bare soil, cover crop in all the lanes, or partial cover crops (understood as alternate lanes of bare soil and cover crop management or narrow, less than 1 m wide, cover crop strips in all the lanes).

These *EVI* values are in [Table S3](#).

2.4. Landscape elements inventory associated with olive orchards

The identification of the landscape elements associated with olive orchards, hereafter LEs, was based on the available information from the inventoried farms ([Section 2.2](#)). This was completed by a detailed analysis of the most updated orthophoto of the National Plan of Aerial Orthophotography (PNOA), obtained in 2016 at 0.5 geometric resolution and Google Earth Pro images (December 2017-December 2018) at the beginning of the study (July 21st, 2018) both at 0.5 geometric resolution through the plugin 'GearthView' which allows a synchronized view. Only the different elements collected in [Table 2](#) and directly associated with the olive farms (adjacent or within them) were considered. The typology of elements, described in [Table 2](#), is an extension of those used by [Mora Jordano \(2009\)](#), starting from a subdivision of them, while trying to maintain concordance with the large categories used in SIGPAC 2018. The identification of the existing LEs was carried out following a systematic scan of the virtual grid described in [Section 2.2](#). Elements that raised some doubts on their interpretation at the image analysis were verified during field visits in June 2019.

Table 2

Landscape elements and complementary information collected in the inventory. LE: landscape element, D: dot, L: line, P: polygon.

Type of LE	QGIS format	Specific characteristics	Restrictions
Isolated trees	D	Within the olive orchard or adjacent to the perimeter.	More than 15 m from the closest tree if there are more than two trees.
Hedgerows	L	Not associated to water courses or wetlands.	
Tree rows	L	Obvious discontinuity between trees.	From 5–15 m of distance between trees. The number of trees must be greater than or equal to 3 trees per row.
Farm boundaries	L	Topographic or physis farm's boundary. If vegetated, only with herbaceous species.	
Paths	L	Agricultural roads directly associated to an olive orchard.	
Terraces	L	Stone walls	
Copses	P	A group of trees.	Maximum separation of 15 m.
Patches	P	Spots of rocks and/or very sparse herbaceous vegetation.	
Buildings	With/without vegetation P	Non-productive zones associated with buildings and their surroundings.	
Thickets	P	Associated to water courses or wetlands.	
Slopes	With/without vegetation P	Height difference associated with communication pathways.	
Gullies	With/without vegetation P		
Water bodies	With/without vegetation P	Ponds, waterways, irrigation ponds and exceptional infrastructures.	
Non cultivated strips/Faces	With/without vegetation P	Non-linear or linear zones not associated with a boundary. If vegetated, only with herbaceous species. It may contain other LEs.	

*Beds ("*bancales*") were not included in this study as the presence of these elements are not representative in the study area.

2.5. Data analysis

The analysis of the results was divided into four stages. In the first there was a preliminary analysis of the evolution of the olive orchard surface between 2005 and 2018, while in the second the calibration and validation of the vegetation indices were used to evaluate the management with or without cover in winter in olive orchards.

The third stage consisted in the analysis of the olive farms in 2018 comparing them with the existing ones in 2005. The farm typologies were established based on different biogeographic (slope and number of different soil types within the farm) and agronomic (tree density, irrigation and ground cover vegetation management) parameters described in [Section 2.2](#). To evaluate the different typologies, the possible relations among these parameters were analysed and complemented by a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and a cluster dendrogram analysis for a hierarchical clustering, both carried out with STATA SE14 ©. Finally, a Kruskal-Wallis test ($P < 0.001$) was carried out to analyse possible differences in some olive orchards' characteristics (e.g., tree density, slope, hedgerow orchards, etc.) between: (i) farms with and without cover crops in winter and (ii) rainfed and irrigated farms.

In the fourth stage, an exploratory analysis was performed regarding the inventoried landscape elements associated with the different olive farms' typologies (e.g., distribution, total number, density, etc.). This information was complemented with a PCA and a cluster dendrogram analysis for a hierarchical clustering, both performed with STATA SE14 ©. This general analysis was completed with a more detailed evaluation of LEs, element by element based on different olive orchards' characteristics: (i) farms with and without cover crops in winter and (ii) rainfed and irrigated farms.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Olive orchards evaluation

3.1.1. Evolution of olive orchards' main features between 2005 and 2018

Considering analytical or descriptive variables, sectoral approaches that classify Andalusian olive orchards are based on their response to certain physical variables that can be considered as determining factors for the implantation, the management and exploitation of olive orchards (e.g., slope, irrigation, or temporal and territorial evolution of the implantation of olives; [Consejería de Cultura, 2018](#)). [Table 3](#) and [Figs. S1](#)

Table 3

Evolution of the olive orchards' surface and characteristics of the existing and new farms in 2005 and 2018.

	2005		2018	
	Surface (ha)	%	Surface (ha)	%
	7997.8		16,447.6	
<i>Tree density (trees/ha)</i>				
< 120	3108.4	38.9	3449.2	21.0
120–200	2872.1	35.9	7023.3	42.7
200–600	1961.2	24.5	4920.9	29.9
600–1000	30.4	0.4	201.7	1.2
> 1000	25.8	0.3	852.4	5.2
<i>Irrigation</i>				
Rainfed	6607.7	82.6	12,564.8	76.4
Irrigated	1390.2	17.4	3882.8	23.6
<i>Slope (%)</i>				
< 5	620.7	7.8	2150.2	13.1
5–10	2561.3	32.0	5686.1	34.6
10–15	3636.8	45.5	7055.1	42.9
15–30	1172.8	14.7	1546.8	9.4
> 30	6.2	0.1	9.3	0.1
<i>Number of different types of soil</i>				
1	7022.1	87.8	13,996.9	85.1
2	951.7	11.9	2417.8	14.7
3	24.0	0.3	32.9	0.2

and S2 show the olive orchard farms in 2005 and the new ones from 2005 to 2018 in the campiña, respectively. Olive trees have roughly doubled their extension during this 13-year period. This is a consequence of market conditions and different agricultural and environmental policies, likely being partially explained by the systematic downward trend in the price of cereals, which has forced farmers to shift to more economically viable crops.

The expansion in recent decades has been associated with higher global productivities (due to the increase in irrigated surface and plantations on soils of better agronomic conditions), resulting in different landscapes and economic typologies considering age plantation and tree densities (Cabrera et al., 2015; Martínez et al., 2011). Our results are in consonance with these studies. This expansion of new orchards has been orientated towards higher plant densities as compared to the previous situation. The orchard type by tree densities that have increased significantly are the ones with density greater than 600 trees/ha, corresponding to super-intensive olive orchards and especially densities greater than 1000 trees/ha, which have gone from 0.3% in 2005–5.2% of the total area of the olive orchards in the campiña in 2018.

This expansion has been accompanied by an increase in the use of irrigation, which is deficit irrigation. It can be appreciated how the rainfed olive orchards' area has decreased. This change means that the irrigated olive grove has almost tripled, from 1390 to 3888 ha, between 2005 and 2018. Despite this expansion of irrigation, the majority of olive orchards remains rainfed, 76.4%.

It is also appreciable how the relative share of olive trees in high and moderate slopes has decreased, from 14.7% in 2005 to 9.4% in 2018 (Table 3). This has been complemented by an increase in the share of olive trees located on milder slopes. So, the share of olive trees on slopes between 5% and 10% and below 5% increased from 32% to 34.6% and from 7.8% to 13.1% respectively. Regarding steep slopes, more than 30%, the increase is marginal, from 0.1% to 0.7%. This wide distribution of slopes is explained by the fact that olive trees are trees which can be adapted to a very wide range of slopes. It is apparent that the growth in olive orchards has been oriented towards moderate slopes and low slopes, areas previously used for arable crops which were preferentially located in soils with the best agronomic aptitude, but also that given the longevity of the orchards the overall picture is still of a crop distributed on a broad range of slopes.

The general distribution of olive orchards by soil types has not undergone a significant change. Our study found most plantations on a unique dominant soil type, more than 87% (Table 3). In 2018, 60.6% of

the olive orchards were in Vertisols compared to 53.7% of the olive orchards in Vertisols when analysed based on the existing plots in 2005, a change that is attributed to the increase in olive orchards during the last decade. These farms on Vertisols are followed by orchards located in Calcareous Fluvisols and Calcareous Regosols, occupying respectively 12.7% and 12.6%. It is also worthy to highlight that this growth has been concentrated in Vertisols and Fluvisols, soils with a high agronomic capacity, which have reduced the relative weight of olive orchards located in Regosols and Cambisols, soils with lower water retention capacity and depth of profile explorable by the roots which tend to be located on the steeper slopes in the campiña.

These variables (tree density, slope and soil type) are directly linked to some of the main environmental issues associated with olive orchards, such as soil degradation use of water resources or mechanization (García-Brenes, 2012). Our results might allow a better appraisal of the evolution of olive cultivation in recent years on these issues, which according to our results seems appreciable, particularly in relation to water use.

3.1.2. Olive orchard soil management evaluation through vegetation indexes

After calculating the value of the eight different vegetation indexes during the calibration process (data shown in Table S4) a Kruskal-Wallis test was performed to determine the three with the most significant correlation with the existing soil management. These indexes were *NDVI*, *GCI* and *EVI* (Table 4) resulting in *EVI* as the best one for detecting three (Table 4a) or two (Table 4b) soil management according to vegetation cover in the lanes during winter in orchards. As expected, we found more statistically significant differences when trying to differentiate between two soil management classes, bare soil vs. some degree of cover crop, than among three (Table 4).

This same trend was observed when analysing the results of the validation exercise, confirming the results of the validation stage, with *EVI* capturing statistically significant differences among the three (as well as two) different soil management classes (Table S5a, b). The verification of the error in determining the soil management during winter for the thirty-four plots used in the validation exercise is shown in Table 5 for distinguishing between three (Table 5a) or two (Table 5b) soil managements. Fig. S3 shows the olive farm distribution in 2018 based on Table 5b classification. Despite the relatively low-resolution images from Sentinel-2 and the inter-row spectral contribution due to

Table 4

Comparison of differences in the vegetation index in winter minus the same index in summer using a Kruskal-Wallis for the calibration exercise with images from 21-II-2019 (winter) vs. 18-VII-2018 (summer): (a) Considering three kinds of lane cover; (b) Considering two kinds of lane cover. *NDVI* is normalized difference vegetation index. *GCI* is green chlorophyll index. *EVI* is enhanced vegetation index.

(a)				
Index	Management	Average rank	H	P
NDVI	Bare soil	12.67	11.290	0.004
	Partial cover crop	16.25		
	Total cover crop	26.58		
GCI	Bare soil	13.58	6.146	0.046
	Partial cover crop	17.75		
	Total cover crop	24.17		
EVI	Bare soil	9.08	21.632	0.000
	Partial cover crop	17.42		
	Total cover crop	29.00		
(b)				
NDVI	Bare soil	22.83	3.050	0.081
	Cover crop	16.33		
GCI	Bare soil	23.33	1.155	0.283
	Cover crop	16.08		
EVI	Bare soil	21.17	3.794	0.051
	Cover crop	17.17		

Table 5

Results of the validation exercise for classifying the olive orchards according to the soil management in winter according to *EVI* vegetation index in winter (EVI_{win}) minus the same index in summer (EVI_{sum}) using a Kruskal-Wallis in the validation exercise comparing images from 21-II-2018 (winter) vs. 21-VII-2017 (summer): (a) Considering three types of lane cover; (b) Considering two kinds of lane cover. *EVI* is enhanced vegetation index. SD is standard deviation, PE is percentage of plots correctly classified ($n = 34$) and L is the $EVI_{win}-EVI_{sum}$ threshold value between soil management classes.

a)						
Management	$EVI_{win}-EVI_{sum}$				PE %	L
	Average	SD	Máx.	Mín.		
Bare soil	0.253	0.072	0.354	0.133	75	0.354
Partial cover crop	0.630	0.203	1.034	0.392		
Total cover crop	0.804	0.220	1.371	0.550		
b)						
Bare soil	0.291	0.111	0.530	0.133	94	0.354
Cover crop	0.717	0.221	1.372	0.392		

the presence of bare soil, ground cover, and shadow pixels (Vélez et al., 2020), this simplified procedure resulted in a high percentage of correctly classified orchards (94%) when trying to detect between bare soil and some kind of cover crop during winter. The percentage of correctly classified orchards decreased to 75% when we tried to distinguish between three management classes with two intensities of cover crop presence during winter (Table 5a). This relatively high error in classification let us concentrate our analysis on discriminating between olive orchards with or without cover crops during the winter period. Our methodology seems to be suitable to discriminate soil management in olive orchards within the range of accuracy found by other authors such as Roquette Tenreiro and Jiménez Berni (2018) through the use of Sentinel-2 images to characterize cover crop development in perennial systems or Peña-Barragán et al. (2004) who implemented a different approach to estimate vegetation fractions using aerial photographs to distinguish between inter-row cover crops, bare soil, and olive canopies with an accuracy of 92%. Although the accuracy of our approach is very much dependent on local calibration, it is not too dissimilar to the correlation found by other authors using Sentinel-2 imagery, e.g. Di Gennaro et al. (2019) who found a correlation with biophysical properties, biomass, yield, ...; in the range of 0.60–0.95 r^2 .

3.1.3. General analysis

The PCA from the agronomic and edapho-geomorphological properties of the olive orchards (surface, slope, tree density, irrigation, slope, soil type and management) explained variance in a relatively large number of components when analysed independently for 2005 and 2018

(70% in the first 4 components in 2018, Table S6a; 2005 not shown), with loads distributed in many different properties (2018 in Table S6b; 2005 not shown) being difficult to assign a determining a dominant weight to an individual property. Our interpretation of this high variability is that no clear difference can be seen between the clusters of the plots already existing in 2005 with those implanted between that date and 2018 (Fig. S4). A cluster analysis considering the above (agronomic and edapho-geomorphological) properties for 2018 (Table S6b) and classifying the olive orchards regarding the most important agronomic variables (tree density and irrigation) shows three main clusters (Fig. S5). One cluster is formed by olive orchards at very low plant density (less than 120 trees/ha), a second cluster if formed by orchards at higher density (more than 600 trees/ha), with a third cluster formed by olives planted at medium-high density (between 120 and 600 trees/ha).

Fig. 2 shows the total surface of olive orchards in the campiña, grouped by tree density and irrigation. It is apparent how a relevant number of plantations (> 73%) still remain below tree densities of 600 trees/ha and rainfed, probably because of lack of access to water resources. Also apparent is a negative correlation between orchard slope and planting density (Fig. 3), which must be one of the major variables behind the clustering shown in Fig. S5.

Considering irrigation in 2018, almost 62% of the olive orchard surface in Andalusia was rainfed (ESYRCE, 2018), which resembles the trend of our results. Regarding tree density, in Andalusia, the extension of olive orchards with more than 1000 trees/ha increases 116% during 2015–2018 (Consejería de Agricultura, Ganadería, Pesca y Desarrollo Sostenible, 2019), representing today approximately 3% of the total olive orchards' extension in the province of Córdoba in 2018, with an increase in the use of irrigation as the plant density increases. Our results shown a higher share of super-intensive orchards in the campiña, 5.2%, which can be explained by the better agronomical aptitude of the soils in the area, and a similar trend towards higher tree density in irrigated orchards (Fig. 2). Nevertheless, it is worthy to note the existence of some rainfed olive plots with more than 1000 trees/ha under rainfed conditions (Fig. 2).

Table 6 compares differences in topographic and soil properties among farms grouped into the two most relevant factors for their agronomic analysis: rainfed or irrigated (a) and use or not of cover crop along the inter tree rows in winter (b). Table 6a shows general trends in some variables, although it is difficult to detect them in a PCA due to the high variability within each group. Irrigated and rainfed farms present differences in the use of vegetation cover with greater use of temporary cover crops in irrigated plots than in rainfed ones, 51% vs. 38% respectively. Rainfed farms seem to be in areas with a slightly higher slope than those irrigated, 10.4% vs. 7.4%, respectively. The irrigated plots have a higher planting density than the rainfed ones, 532 vs. 189

Fig. 2. Surface of olive orchards regarding tree density and irrigation system. Numbers on the bars indicate the % of each class regarding the total surface.

Fig. 3. Average slope of the olive orchards regarding tree density and irrigation system.

Table 6

a) Comparison of some characteristics of olive farms (a) between rainfed and irrigated plots and (b) between bare soil and cover crop plots, for some topographic and agronomic characteristics: hedgerow plantations, use of cover crops, tree density, average, maximum and minimum slope. In both cases, a summary of the two classes is included. *** means significant differences ($P < 0.001$) from a Kruskal-Wallis test. NS: not significant.

a)						
Class	Hedgerow orchards (%)	Cover crops (%)	Tree density (trees/ha)	Average slope (%)	Min. slope (%)	Max. slope (%)
Rainfed	2.3	37.9	189.5	10.4	4.1	17.5
Irrigated	17.2	50.5	532.5	7.4	2.0	16.2
<i>P</i>	***	***	***	***	***	***
Class	Dominant soil type		Total area (ha)		Cover crop area (ha)	
Rainfed	Vertisol		12564.8		4765.8	
Irrigated	Vertisol		3882.8		1960.9	
b)						
Class	Hedgerow orchards (%)	Irrigated (%)	Tree density (trees/ha)	Average slope (%)	Min. slope (%)	Max. slope (%)
Bare soil	4.1	9.6	223.0	9.4	3.4	16.5
Cover crop	4.2	14.9	240.4	11.0	4.5	18.7
<i>P</i>	NS	***	NS	***	***	***
Class	Dominant soil type		Total area (ha)			
Bare soil	Vertisol		10,014.8			
Cover crop	Vertisol		6432.8			

trees/ha, respectively. The fraction of plots with olive trees forming hedgerows is also clearly higher in irrigated orchards, 18% vs. 2%, respectively. In both cases the dominant soil type is Vertisols.

Table 6b shows some trends that are difficult to detect in the PCA as well. For example, orchards using a temporary cover crop tend to be in areas with a slightly higher average slope (11.0 vs. 9.4%), and these orchards using cover crops, have a higher use of irrigation than those with bare soil, 14.9% vs. 9.6% respectively. This is in line with the trend observed in Spain’s olive orchard surface, as a whole (ESYRCE, 2019). This study reported that in 2019 minimum tillage was the most common management to keep bare soil (40%) followed by cover crops, mainly of spontaneous vegetation (28%). Colombo et al. (2020) estimated that in Andalusia cover crops were 29% of the total Andalusian olive surface, although during 2009–2019 the increase in olive orchards using temporary cover crops was of 122,705 ha. Our results show a slightly higher use of cover crops in the campiña than in the overall Spanish and

Andalusian trend, which might be related to a higher presence of irrigation and higher technical qualification by farmers in the study area (Gómez et al., 2021). Temporary cover crops are used in 39% of the total olive orchards’ area, with a higher frequency of use by irrigated olive orchards, 50.5% of the time, as compared to 37.9% of the time in rainfed olive orchards. In rainfed orchards cover crop management seems to be greater extended in more sparse plant densities, below 600 trees/ha, while it is only occasionally used above that plant density, probably reflecting the farmers’ difficulty balancing cover crop management and adequate water availability for the tree. On the contrary, in irrigated orchards, cover crop management seems to be implemented in a more distributed way, especially in orchards with 200–600 trees/ha, likely due to the availability of water for crop consumption. In most cases, cover crops are present at all plantation densities except in those with more than 1000 trees/ha, which might be explained by this orchard typology being among the most recent and ground cover vegetation is still strictly controlled to avoid possible water competition with young olive trees.

Our results also show how cover crops were used in many different typologies of olive orchards in the campiña, (Fig. 4). Gómez et al. (2021) surveyed 57 olive growers in the same study area from June–December 2019. Their results were in line with the ones from this study, concluding in a significant use of temporary cover crops, the ones based on the management and control (mowing, herbicides and/or plowing) of the existing spontaneous vegetation on the farms being predominant. It is possible that the differences between olive orchards of different tree densities are due to socioeconomic variables that are beyond this study, although they suggest the need to evaluate them in detail to expand the adoption of the use of covers, which is still recommended in a landscape with a clear risk of erosion and low biodiversity.

3.2. Landscape elements associated with current olive orchards

3.2.1. General analysis

From the PCA of landscape elements (Table S7a,b) and cluster analysis (Fig. S6) of similarity on density of landscape elements among orchards classes grouped by tree density and access to irrigation, the tendency to differences in the landscape element due to orchard differences in features like tree density and use of irrigation is apparent (Fig. S6). Given the aforementioned correlation between tree density and slope of the orchards, it might be possible that this grouping partially reflects the effect of topography on the ease of persistence of landscape elements in the study area. The combined effect of irrigation and moderate and high tree densities (more than 200 trees/ha) with landscape elements, is also reflected in Fig. 5. This segregation between tree density and trend with irrigated farms is also reflected in the values of the PC1, whose variables with highest loads represents key landscape

Fig. 4. Surface of olive orchards with bare soil and cover crops regarding tree density and irrigation system. Numbers on the bars indicate the % of each class regarding the total surface.

Fig. 5. Load on the first two main components (PC1 and PC2) discriminating between intensive olive groves and the rest in relation to landscape elements.

elements such as slopes, buildings, water bodies or patches, all polygonal elements and with a high potential to implement revegetation and restoration measures), (Fig. 6, Table S7).

Fig. 7 shows the overall length and extension of the linear and polygonal landscape elements associated with the olive orchards in our study, while Figs. 8 and 9 disaggregate the more relevant ones according to the tree density and irrigation use to be further described in the following Section.

3.2.2. Detailed analysis of specific landscape elements

3.2.2.1. Isolated trees and linear elements. A total of 507 isolated trees have been found distributed within and/or on the perimeter of the plots, (Fig. S7). Fig. 8 shows the average length in relation to each olive orchard typology of the linear LEs. An overall of 677 linear elements were inventoried (Fig. S8) resulting in a total length of 343.93 km in length corresponding to 13.76 km of tree rows, 178.02 km of paths, and 148.62 km of farm boundaries.

Total hedgerow length, mostly discontinuous, was 1.65 km. Hedgerows tended to appear mostly in rainfed olive orchards, 75%, (generally

of greater length) and especially in plots with tree densities lower than 200 trees/ha. The scarce sections of hedgerows reflect the lack of correlations with other topographic properties. We did not evaluate the quality of conservation of these hedgerows. However, in his study in the campiña, Mora Jordano (2009) found that 71% (3.6 linear km within 5.4 km of total length) of the hedgerows of the Cordoba countryside were degraded and poorly preserved and only 29% (1.8 km) were in an acceptable condition. Casual observations of the hedgerows inventoried in our study also suggest a significant variability in their conservation status, indicating their potential for becoming a priority element to restore in the campiña landscape, including olive orchards.

In terms of farm boundaries, (341 sections) the 68% were, as expected, associated with the most frequent orchards in the area: rainfed and with tree densities ranging from 120 to 600 trees/ha. We also found 81 groups of tree rows and 236 sections of paths associated with olive orchards, with an average length per element unit of 0.17 km and 0.75 km, respectively. Both elements are related to each other (e.g., tree rows along the paths to rural buildings) being more frequent in rainfed olive orchards and in general terms, in orchards with tree densities in the range of 120–600 trees/ha. The average length of paths and rural roads,

Fig. 6. Components' loadings for PC1 and PC2 from the PCA of the association of the different landscape elements (points, linear and polygonal) and olive orchards.

Fig. 7. Length of linear landscape elements (LEs) and surface of polygonal LEs in the Cordoba countryside. Polygonal elements associated with vegetation are also specified. Numbers on the bars indicate the total number of elements within each category.

another landscape element with a large potential to concentrate actions for improving provision of ecosystem services, was shorter in rainfed plots (0.70 km) compared to irrigated ones (0.92 km). This difference could be attributed to the fact that irrigated olive groves are mainly associated with low slopes that facilitate the passage and construction of roads, as well as the higher degree of investment in this type of olive orchard.

3.2.2.2. Polygonal elements. 1524 polygonal elements have been inventoried covering a fragmented area of 714.03 ha, across the campiña (Fig. S9). It is noteworthy that, except for the areas around buildings, there is a significant fraction of these polygonal elements that are unvegetated, around 45% and 42% on slopes and gullies, respectively and on the banks of water courses and strips/faces (55% and 87%, respectively), Fig. 7. This indicates the high potential of these areas to

implant autochthonous vegetation. Thus, these vegetated interstices could act as nodes for the restoration of biodiversity and improvement of hydrological functions and protection against soil erosion. Even in areas with some degree of vegetation there is potential for an improvement in the vegetation cover by making it denser and more diverse. This is apparent in the case of gully areas, which tend to have fragmented vegetation and lack the capacity to effectively control erosion in episodes of intense rain.

Fig. S10 shows the density of all polygonal elements associated with different olive orchard typologies. Based on their extension and representativeness in the study area, a more detailed analysis of the most relevant ones is presented in Fig. 9. These major elements are thickets, water bodies, gullies, non-cultivated areas/strips and buildings. As defined in Table 2, thickets are associated with water courses or wetlands (being conformed by woody and herbaceous vegetation) or could

Fig. 8. Linear landscape elements associated with olive orchards regarding tree density and irrigation. Numbers on the bars indicate the total number of elements within each category.

Fig. 9. Most extended polygonal landscape elements associated with olive orchards regarding tree density and irrigation: thickets, water bodies, gullies, non-productive areas/strips and buildings. Numbers on the bars indicate the total number of elements within each category.

present some vegetation elements, in the case of the last four, Fig. 7.

Of the 191.7 ha inventoried of thickets, their distribution seems unequal, with more than 56% of their surface on low slopes (< 5%), 82% adjacent to irrigated plots and 60% in orchards using a cover crop. Of the 153.9 ha of water bodies, they appeared more frequently adjacent to bare soil and rainfed orchards, both in a 77%. There are 55.7 ha of non-productive areas/strips, being the only polygonal LE existing in slopes higher than 30%, with a total surface of 0.23 ha. In the case of gully surface, their extension is greater in bare soil and rainfed orchards (65% and 89%, respectively), with the highest gully density in orchards located in the 15–30% slopes (0.04 ha/ha).

In all cases these landscape elements remained unvegetated (Fig. 7) and are noteworthy for their great potential for using autochthonous vegetation (from herbaceous to shrubs and trees) to enhance the quality of the landscape in this olive growing area while simultaneously improving the provision of other ecosystem services, such as soil erosion prevention, conservation of soil fertility, the regulation of hydrological cycle and improvement in habitat for enhancing biodiversity.

3.2.3. Landscape elements and ecosystem provisioning in orchards under Mediterranean conditions

The inventory of these major features for provision of ecosystem services in the study area that might be representative of other areas of intense olive cultivation in the Mediterranean basin. The 16,447.6 ha of olive orchards had an associated total area of 714.0 ha of polygonal LEs plus 343.9 km of linear LEs, with only 507 isolated trees. Among the lineal elements, paths, and farm boundaries, most of them unvegetated, are the dominant elements (almost 95% of the total length of the linear LEs), with 1.7 km of hedgerows with different conservation degrees. These linear LEs were evenly spread between irrigated and rainfed orchards, with the exception of paths that tended to be more frequent in the irrigated orchards, probably associated with a higher investment and level of intensification. Among the polygonal LEs, thickets were the most extended, 191.7 ha, associated with permanent water courses. They were followed by water bodies, of which there were 153.8 ha, most of them ephemeral streams and some small water reservoirs, and gullies,

another 153.3 ha. Gullies were more frequent in the bare soil managed orchards and in the slope class of 15–30%, although they are still present on other milder slopes and some cover crop managed orchards. There were also 55.7 ha of non-productive areas/strips, this being the only polygonal LE existing on slopes higher than 30%. Approximately 65% of the area of these three LEs remained unvegetated and those vegetated were mostly sparsely covered. They provide a good opportunity for implanting vegetation to improve the provision of ecosystem services with a minimum impact on farm operations and yield.

Certain regions across Europe, such as the ones located in the Mediterranean basin or the one described in this study, show a remarkable potential for accommodating semi-natural vegetation within their agricultural areas (García-Feced et al., 2015) but their actual implantation and associated potential of benefits provisioning ecosystem services depends on local agricultural practices (e.g. carbon sequestration as reported by Parras-Alcántara and Lozano-García, 2014 or Vicente-Vicente et al., 2016). They need to be adapted to the agronomic needs of the farms while simultaneously creating adequate conditions for implantation of semi-natural vegetation within the limits imposed by local environmental conditions.

Despite it seeming clear that the preservation of landscape in rural areas is a profitable policy strategy and that habitat heterogeneity at landscape and local scales is a key element for biodiversity, the number of studies addressing landscape configuration in agricultural areas as a conductor of provisioning ecosystem services is still scarce (Paiola et al., 2020). However, the effect of landscape heterogeneity through natural or semi-natural elements and farming intensity on biodiversity is still difficult to disaggregate. For instance, in the study carried out by Hall et al. (2020) in vineyards across Europe, it was found that more intensive management intensities resulted in lower species richness, functional diversity and vegetation cover, whereas landscape diversity increased plant species richness only slightly. They also noted that nationwide differences in edaphoclimatic conditions was a significant factor in explaining differences in diversity and functional traits. In particular, Rodríguez-Entrena et al. (2017) noted the added value of improving esthetics at olive growing areas through vegetation elements (cover crops) and other landscape elements (stone walls, wood islets). These landscape features contribute positively to the rural areas' economy, not only through the use of landscape and the performance of related leisure activities, but also due to the provision of environmental benefits such as carbon sequestration, soil erosion control or enhancement of biodiversity. Among natural and semi-natural elements, hedgerows/field margins or farm boundaries, woodland and grassland are usually the most heavily investigated in relation to provisioning ecosystem services regarding biological control, pollination, or soil conservation, but most of them are associated with field crops (Holland et al., 2017). Considering the large extension of tree crops across Europe, more than 13.3 M ha (Gómez, 2016), this points to a significant research gap worth addressing. Concepción et al. (2020) also noted the need not only for preventing landscape simplification for biodiversity conservation but also for addressing it in a more comprehensive approach beyond adding new landscape elements without a conceptual framework for its impact.

In winegrowing areas of Italy, Aimar et al. (2021) concluded that landscape changes are driven mainly by local and context-dependent dynamics, it being necessary to design customized policies and landscape planning and management based on land uses and historical permanencies to optimize the development of multifunctional agricultural landscapes. In slope and mountainous olive orchards of Portugal Fleskens et al. (2009) noted that provided ecological functions were low although these orchards were essential for maintaining, among other ecosystem services, the cultural landscape and rural economy. In other Mediterranean intensifying farming landscapes, such as the study area with an increasing expansion of high tree density and irrigated olive orchards, land management decisions should strive to maintain the existing semi-natural elements and fragments; hedgerows and vegetated

boundaries should be established along margins in areas where natural habitats have already been replaced by agriculture (Heath et al., 2017). Agri-environment schemes in the Mediterranean should therefore promote landscape heterogeneity through the conservation and/or the restoration of semi-natural habitats (e.g., crop margins with hedgerows, tree rows, or remnant riparian vegetation) in the surrounding landscape of orchards at multiple spatial scales (Alignier et al., 2021).

All these research questions require a comprehensive inventory of existing landscapes elements, current status and the potential incorporation of new ones in relation to farm characteristics for a better pairing in agronomic and environmental goals. This study presents such appraisal for a representative case study area and therefore, could serve as an example for other undergoing areas under olive tree (or other woody crop) intensification in fertile areas of the Mediterranean basin.

4. Conclusions

This study presents a systematic analysis of the effects, on olive orchard typology, of the increase in the area of cultivated olive orchards using a case study in the campiña of Cordoba in Southern Spain. This increase has been performed in detriment of arable land (mainly cropped with cereals) in fertile areas of the Guadalquivir River Valley. It is accompanied by an inventory of landscape elements in these orchards and their potential for improving ecosystem services.

In this study, it has been documented how olive orchards have almost doubled their extension. As a result, the current situation of olive cultivation in the study area remains as a mosaic of orchard types, in terms of water use, plant densities and slopes, although within a general trend towards intensification. In addition, the implementation of environmentally-sustainable management practices, such as temporary cover crops vs. bare soil management, remains mixed in the area despite their being a key tool for soil erosion control or enhancement of biodiversity.

The identification of potential landscape elements or non-productive areas associated with olive orchards is crucial to implementing and designing effective revegetation and restoration measurements. Considering that there are already guidelines and successful examples for revegetation of these landscape elements adapted to the region (e.g., Gómez et al., 2019), vegetation of these linear and polygonal landscape elements should be prioritized in the incoming CAP period as a straightforward way to achieve more sustainable olive production. Inventories like the one presented in this study, including variability as a major factor as soil management is for agroecosystems, would be relatively easy to perform through free available information and remote-sensing images and could be very useful to monitor the impact of landscape changes and identify susceptible areas of being degraded.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106065](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106065).

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